

Modern solutions for middle span steel-concrete composite bridges in Poland: hybrid girders and rolled sections using high strength steel and weathering steel

Tomasz Kołakowski^a, Witold Kosecki^a, Henryk Windorpski^b,
Adam Stempniewicz^c, Błażej Bartoszek^c, Wojciech Lorenc^{*,d}, Maciej Kozuch^d, Piotr Koziol^d

^aEuroprojekt Gdańsk S.A. , Poland
t.kolakowski@europrojekt.pl, w.kosecki@europrojekt.pl

^bCreator Sp. z o.o., Poland
h.windorpski@pi-creator.pl

^cFasys Mosty, Poland
biuro@fasysmosty.pl

^dWrocław University of Science and Technology, Dept. of Civil, Environmental, Poland
wojciech.lorenc@pwr.edu.pl, maciej.kozuch@pwr.edu.pl, piotr.koziol@pwr.edu.pl

ABSTRACT

The expansion of the highway network in Poland and the introduction of the design-and-build system have resulted in new varieties of medium-span composite bridges. In addition, there is ongoing reconstruction of the railway network. The market of composite bridges in Poland is characterized by high degree of dynamism with constant changes and innovations. The introduction of composite dowels has led to the creation of new forms of bridges, including the latest ones using the so-called hybrid cross-section. Simultaneously, the commonly used rolled sections made of S460 steel are now replaced by weathering steel S460W. The combination of these solutions creates bridge forms different from those previously used. This paper presents examples of designed and built bridges.

Keywords: composite dowels, hybrid section, composite bridges, steel-concrete bridges

1 INTRODUCTION

The introduction of composite dowels in Europe at the beginning of the last decade led to the creation of new forms of composite bridges, in which a T-profile is used instead of an I-beam. The driving force behind this development was the PreCoBeam project (1). The initial outcomes of the project resulted in the construction of various bridges across several European countries (2). In the early stages, various individual solutions were introduced in an attempt to find the appropriate market sector for the new forms and design methods have evolved. During this period, the road network was undergoing intensive expansion in Poland, and the adoption of the design-and-build formula compelled design companies, among others, to look for new solutions. New bridges were built to test various innovations and new solutions, including composite dowels, HL1100 sections using S460 steel grade, weathering steel, and others. Presently, both the construction and design methods are new, comparing to the situation from over 10 years ago. Guidelines for the designing of a shear connection were developed, and concepts for the designing of a hybrid steel-concrete sections for bridges has been established (3); this will be introduced in the new CEN-TS 1994-1-102 specification. The solutions presented in Figs. 1-3, which were considered “old” in Poland, laid the foundations for new, more economical systems; as described in (4). Simultaneously, "ordinary" rolled I-beams of the HL type were introduced but adapted for constructing bridges with spans of 50- 60 m (5). Different solutions were used for railway bridges (7) and different ones for road bridges, and over time, some ideas began to overlap. A separate issue, but of significant importance for the development of the composite bridge market, is the introduction of weathering S460W steel. The first bridge in the EU

employing this steel was designed and built in Poland. Currently, there are essentially two types of solutions (with composite dowels) for road bridges, depending on the span length, and a separate group of solutions for railway bridges (with ongoing development of some individual solutions).

Fig. 1. The second generation of bridges by composite dowels and respective composite sections (4): a) bridge P11 constructed in Romania, b) bridge PE4 constructed in Poland, c) bridge “Simmerbach” constructed in Germany, d) bridge over Łososina river (Wierna Rzeka bridge) constructed in Poland next to Kielce, e) viaduct in Kuchl constructed in Austria, f) viaduct WD4, at S5 road near to Bydgoszcz, constructed in Poland.

Fig. 2. Elbląg bridge (6) designed by Europrojekt Gdańsk S. A. with 38m spans: an example of the solution used about 10 years ago in Poland.

Fig. 3. Bridge in Sobieszewo designed by Europrojekt Gdańsk S. A. (4): introduction of so called “transition zone”.

2 ROAD BRIDGES UP TO 40M USING COMPOSITE DOWELS AND HYBRID CONCEPT

An important factor, irrespective of the implementation of the T-section concept in composite bridges, was the incorporation of S460W steel. Thanks to this, composite bridges gained a competitive edge over their concrete counterparts, and composite solutions began to be further developed. The first bridge is a classic composite structure (Fig. 4). However, following its completion, S460W steel was used in the T-sections for solutions with composite dowels. Notably, since the bridge's construction in 2020, approximately 30 bridges made of this steel have been built (or are currently under construction) in Poland - this shows the pace of development of the solution on the market. After building the bridges shown in Figs. 3 and 4, it became evident that the future development of composite dowels for the coming years would be to use a concrete section at the supports and reduce the web thickness.

Fig. 4. Road bridge in Wirkowice: the first bridge in Europe constructed with S460 grade weathering steel (S460J2W) - design by Fasys Mosty.

This required, among other things, the development of the so-called transition zone between the steel and concrete cross-sections. Destructive tests were performed on a natural scale (Fig. 5) to evaluate the solution.

Fig. 5. Full scale tests of beams with transition zone for purposes of the bridge in Sobieszewo.

The solutions were initially tested on short-span bridges: bridge in Biskupice (Fig. 6) uses transition zone, thin concrete web and S460W steel. This bridge followed a similar one but with a plate instead of concrete web (Fig. 7). There is an important point hidden in this seemingly insignificant change shown in Fig. 7: by utilizing the appropriate depth of steel in the concrete and properly placing the reinforcement, it becomes possible to eliminate the criterion of concrete failure due to the pry out (8).

Fig. 6. Road bridge over the Giełczew River in Biskupice - cross-section of the bridge and longitudinal section (design by Fasys Mosty).

This aspect delves into the fundamental principles of composite dowel shear connection design, which are not covered by current design guidelines. The introduction of this solution involved challenging research and tests (Fig. 8) and, at the same time, the introduction of the hybrid cross-section concept (significant R&D effort) according to (3).

Fig. 7. The section of the bridge Biskupice (left) vs previous solution (right).

Fig. 8. The tests of hybrid beams with 30cm and 20cm web (Wrocław Univ. of Science and Technology)

Upon confirming the efficacy of the solution, the two major difficulties standing in the way of the widespread use of hybrid beams in the market were overcome. A solution was devised wherein a thin concrete web with a thickness of 20 cm could sufficiently transfer large shear using a composite dowel connection in such a way that the pry-out cone criterion does not occur. This solution, known as strongly reinforced composite dowels SRCD (8), and together with hybrid concept for the cross-section constitutes the basis for the modern design of hybrid beams in Poland. It has been implemented in the construction of many bridges on the new S3 highway. These bridges are currently under construction (year 2024).

Fig. 9. Viaducts with hybrid beams (over the newly constructed S3 highway) and the long bridge with hybrid beams (along the newly constructed S3 highway) in northern Poland: design by Europrojekt Gdańsk.

The system shown in Fig. 9 was used for the first time, and currently, it is utilized for bridges with spans up to 36 m. However, there is no limitation preventing its application for larger spans, and such expansions are part of the future plans. For spans exceeding 50 m, a modification of the solution from railway bridges is used, so these will be presented first.

3 RAILWAY BRIDGES

Two primary solutions are commonly employed for railway bridges. The first one is a modification of the solution used for purposes of the "Wiarna Rzeka" bridge (9) shown in Fig. 1d, and allows reducing the consumption of structural steel compared to filler beam decks by approximately 50%. The bridge shown in Fig. 10 is designed following the hybrid section concept (3) and incorporates the shear connection using composite dowels that is designed to eliminate pry-out cone failure (8); as shown in Fig. 11. The second type of railway bridges is much more complicated from design point of view (3).

Fig. 10. The viaduct in Dąbrowa Górnicza w km 300,009 designed by FasysMosty and built by Nowak Mosty: solution with composite dowels (left: b) was used as alternative to filler beam deck (left: a) and constructed viaduct (nowak-mosty.pl)

Fig. 11. The system of reinforcement according to hybrid section concept for railway bridges.

Fig. 12. The another viaduct in Dąbrowa Górnicza designed by FasysMosty (left) and built by Nowak Mosty (right: picture by Nowak Mosty)

Fig. 13. Construction of viaduct in Dąbrowa Górnicza: a) steel sections (by ArcelorMittal) b) steel shapes and reinforcement (by Nowak Mosty), c,d) first load test

The implementation of this straightforward (and cost-effective) structure provided valuable experience in global analysis, section design, and implementation. This acquired knowledge is currently applied in other projects, as detailed in (6). While the distribution of shear in this complex section (Fig. 14) is not an easy task (10) but it can be conservatively done using hybrid section concept according to (3).

Fig. 14. Distribution of shear in the span section of viaduct in Dąbrowa Górnicza (by B. Bartoszek)

4 ROAD BRIDGES WITH SPANS OVER 50M USING COMPOSITE DOWELS AND HYBRID CONCEPT

Currently, a new system, known as the “crocodile”, is being implemented for spans exceeding 50 m. The origins of this system were a modification of the system (different and new in its time) for constructing composite bridges with spans of approximately 50 m. This involved the use of a rolled I-beam in the span zone and separate I-beams with a welded web plate in the support zone, as described in (5). Several bridges were built in this system, but the first one was the bridge in Opole (Figs. 15,16), proving that rolled I-sections are an economical and durable solution for bridges with spans also over 40 m (this was the upper span limit previously in Poland for rolled sections). Continuously implemented general idea of maximization of consumption of hot-rolled sections

instead of welded plates led to many combinations of applied solutions (5). In the meantime application of composite dowels has been considered simultaneously to improve offered solutions. Finally, after successful implementation of new railway bridge in Dąbrowa (Figs. 10,11,12), the new concept, so called "crocodile", was proposed and it is being developed in Poland right now (first bridge is already under construction).

Fig. 15. Bridge in Opole: midspan section (upper) and support section (lower).

Fig. 16. Bridge in Opole: steel part using T-sections and additional plate (left) and the bridge (right).

The “crocodile” girder consists of longitudinally cut HL section with a composite dowel line (obtaining two steel T-sections with composite dowels) and a concrete web between these T-sections (see Figs. 18-20). The variable height of the girder, with the bottom T-section inclined, and the “teeth” of composite dowels create the appearance of "crocodile jaws" in the side view. It is a good example how the initial simple idea can evolve into a complex composite solution that becomes a new marked product, more economical than traditional ones (5).

Fig. 17. Chosen ideas for intermediate support zones in bridges with spans out of HL1100 sections leading to development of a “crocodile” solution: a) upside-down view of cross section of Dąbrowa bridge (6), b) Elbląg bridge (7), c) “crocodile” solution, d) Opole or Rzuchów bridge (5).

Fig. 17 shows how the implementation of various ideas leads to their interpenetration and the creation of a new solution. Fig. 20 shows the connection zone between a part with a constant height and a part

with a variable height and it is visible that there are three types of connectors used in composite structures: welded studs (WS), perfbond strip (PBL) and composite dowels (CD). This is also a feature of the composite solutions currently in development in Poland, and the increasing use of PBL is inspired by close collaboration with Japanese engineers (11). In Japan, PBL, despite being invented in Europe, is a common type of shear connection. The steel consumption for the bridge over Kwisa is 139 kg/m^2 (the length of the middle span is 55.6m), making this solution appear highly economical and robust (no ribs, weathering steel etc.).

Fig. 18. Idea of “crocodile” solution – rolled sections with concrete web (side view).

Fig. 19. Idea of “crocodile” solution – rolled sections with concrete web: cross sections is mid-span (left) and at the support (right).

Fig. 20. Steel parts of “crocodile” girder: different types of shear connection at the left (WS: welded studs, PBL: perfbond, CD: composite dowels) and production of steel parts in Luxembourg (picture by ArcelorMittal)

Fig. 21. Bridge over Kwisa river using “crocodile” system and S460W steel: longitudinal section (design by Creator).

Fig. 22. Bridge over Kwisa river: cross section over the pillar using hybrid beams (design by Creator).

5 SUMMARY

The modern solutions used in Polish medium-span composite bridges are presented. The development of MCL-shaped composite dowels, the introduction of the hybrid cross-section concept, and the subsequent modification of the solution to SRCD (thin concrete webs) have enabled the virtually unconstrained design of composite structures, a possibility not feasible two decades ago. The boundary between reinforced concrete and steel structures has blurred, giving rise to innovative solutions that are continuously evolving. The presented solutions are subject to ongoing optimization, and new designs are approached in a slightly different way; it is a continuous process. The Polish market is dynamic (a lot of bridges are being built), very competitive (companies from Poland, Germany, Scandinavia, Austria, etc. compete) and design is conditioned by the design-and-build formula. This is an important issue that motivates design offices for constant development of their offered solutions. The European design guidelines (12), which are currently being completed, are intended to enable broader design of the described type of structure.

REFERENCES

1. **Seidl G.** et al. RFCS research project PrEco-Beam : *Prefabricated enduring composite beams based on innovative shear transmission*. EUR 25321 EN. Brussels, European Commission, 2013.
2. **Seidl G., Stambuk M., Lorenc W., Kolakowski T., Petzek E.** *Wirtschaftliche Verbundbauweisen im Brückenbau - Bauweisen mit Verbunddübelleisten*. Stahlbau 82 (2013), Heft 7: 510-521.
3. **Lorenc W., Kurz W. Seidl G.** *Hybrid steel – concrete sections for bridges: Definition and basis for design*. Engineering Structures 270 (2022) 114902.
4. **Lorenc, W.** *Composite dowels: the way to the new forms of steel-concrete composite structures*. Wrocław : IABSE Symposium 7-9 October 2020, 2020.
5. **Kożuch M., Lorenc W., Bartoszek B., Stempniewicz A., Windorpski H., Struczyński M., Sęk R., Ochojski W.** *Application of rolled sections in composite bridges with span over 50 meters*. 9th International Conference On Composite Construction In Steel And Concrete, 2021. Stromberg, Germany, July 26-30, 2021.
6. **Lorenc W., Bartoszek B.** *The new railway hybrid bridge in Dąbrowa Górnicza: innovative concept using new design method and results of load tests*. Studia Geotechnica et Mechanica, 2023; 1–23.
7. **Lorenc W., Kolakowski T., Hukowicz A., Seidl G.** *Verbundbrücke bei Elbląg Weiterentwicklung der VFT-WIB-Bauweise*. Stahlbau 86 (2017), Heft 2.
8. **Lorenc W., Seidl G.** *Composite dowels for bridges: trends and challenges for new European design rules*. 9th International Conference On Composite Construction In Steel And Concrete, 2021. Stromberg, Germany, July 26-30, 2021.
9. **Lorenc W.** *Concrete failure of composite dowels under cyclic loading during full-scale tests of beams for the “Wiarna Rzeka” bridge*. Engineering Structures 2020; 209:1 – 14.
10. **Lorenc W.** *The model for a general composite section resulting from the introduction of composite dowels*. Steel Construction 10 (2017):154-167.
11. **Ohyama O., Imagawa Y., Koziol P.** *PBL shear connection in bridges*. Wrocławskie Dni Mostowe 2022 (WDM Conference 2022: Wrocław Bridge Days 2022) 2022.
12. **CEN/TC 250 prCEN/TS 1994-1-102.** *Eurocode 4 — Design of composite steel and concrete structures – Part 1-102: Composite Dowels*.